

Effectiveness of structured teaching program on impact of mobile phone addiction on academic performance among students of degree college

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Abstract:

The whole world is gripped by the mobile craze, whether it is a student, house wife, shopkeeper, rickshaw driver, and milkman professional, rich or poor almost everyone carries a cell phone in his/ her hand. A mobile phone must have item for many average teenagers. Many people spend more than six hours a day on their phones in talking, texting and playing games. The extensive use of cell phone is making us addict of this small device. Just like every medicine has its side effect, cell phone also has its drawbacks. The increased usage of mobile phone has increased magnitude of potential health risk, academic and work performance among its users. Mobile phone has become an integral part of daily life, especially among college students. While mobile phones support communication and learning, excessive and uncontrolled use can lead to mobile phone addiction, negatively affecting students' academic performance, concentration, and mental well-being. Degree college students are particularly vulnerable to mobile phone addiction due to increase academic demands, social media exposure, and easy internet access.

The present study aims to assess the effectiveness of structural teaching programme (STP) on knowledge regarding the impact of mobile phone addiction on academic performance among degree college students. A quantitative research approach with pre-experiment alone-group pre-test and post-test research design was adopted for study. The data were collected by using structured questionnaire from 50 students in a selected college of Jammu by purposive sampling technique. The STP was administered after the pres-test, followed by a post-test to evaluate its effectiveness. The finding of the study revealed a significant improvement in the post-test knowledge scores (26% of participants had inadequate knowledge (0-10 score), while 74% had moderate knowledge (11-12score), and only 0% had adequate knowledge (21-30 score) when compared to the pre-test scores(88% participants had adequate knowledge, and only 12% remain in the moderate knowledge range),indicating that the STP was effective in enhancing students knowledge regarding the impact of mobile phone usage on academic performance. The study highlights the importance of educational interventions in promoting responsible mobile phone usage among college students to improve academic outcomes.

Keywords:

Structural teaching program, Impact, Addition, Mobile phone, Academic performance etc.
